

NCF4, a CGD susceptibility gene, functions through Ly75 and the VEO IBD variant TRIM22.

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NCF4 p40 PHOX deficiency was recently identified as a candidate susceptibility gene for autosomal recessive CGD-3 (2). CGD, like fistulizing IBD in patients with Crohn's Disease, results in specific clinical presentation with colitis-like symptoms and perianal disease in the context of autoimmunity and inflammatory disease (1). The disease in humans with chronic granulomatous disease (CGD) and subtype B3 Crohn's Disease (IBD) penetrating disease is thought to be hematopoietic-derived, studied primarily in the context of the neutrophil in CGD (3). We studied *Ncf4* network composition using transcriptomic co-regulation to identify causative cooperating factors in penetrating autoimmune inflammatory GI disease with clinical need. We describe here selective expression of *Ncf4* in Cd16- monocytes in humans using systems biologic transcriptomic profiling for *Ncf4*-associated settings and neighborhood analysis in *Ncf4*-associated signaling pathways or settings. We identified central *Ncf4* interaction nodes using neighborhood analysis. Genes co-regulated with *Ncf4* in Cd16- monocytes included *Ms4a6a*, *Clec4d*, *Fpr1*, *Cd99*, *Cxhc5* and *Ly75-Cd302*, indicating involvement of innate immune receptors of the Ly, membrane spanning and Clec families in immune cell recruitment or a cell-mediated process. Lymphocyte antigens are important for tolerance and transplant immunity pertinent to self non-self recognition mechanisms active during development and in disease like cancer and IBD. We recently described control of the Ly antigen family by the Crohn's Disease susceptibility gene *Nod2* and demonstrated their misexpression in transplant settings (4, 5). *Ly75* was separately identified as an inflammatory bowel disease risk factor in a genome-wide association study to identify novel IBD susceptibility loci (6, 7). To study contributions of *Ly75* to the penetrating disease process and characterize the *Ly75* (*Cd205/Dec205*) - *Ncf4* interaction, we measured total expression in human cells with targeted depletion of *Ly75*. A primary transcriptional consequence of *Ly75* loss in cells was activation of the *Ncf* family gene *Ncf3*, supporting existence of biologically relevant, cross-tissue interaction between the *Ncf* family and *Ly75*. We studied the *Ly75*-depleted transcriptome to obtain insight into mechanisms by which *Ly75* influenced function or structure of the immune cell. *Cdkn2a* was silenced by *Ly75* depletion, and cycling dependent kinase *Cdk6* was activated, indicating cell cycle control was a general property of the Lymphocyte antigen family. We recently demonstrated that *Gpr84* identified B3 subtype in humans with IBD, and that the *Gpr84* marker was specifically activated following gram negative bacterial infection in CGD mutant but not wild-type cells indicating *Gpr84* was a marker of penetrating disease (8, 9). *Gpr84* was not activated by *Ly75* depletion. However, *Ly75* depletion did result in induction of *Tnfrsf14*, the ligand for the LIGHT receptor, a molecule recently identified both as specific pathway vulnerability in humans with penetrating subtype B3 IBD, as well a critical component of the MDP-inducible gene expression program in monocytes and macrophage (10-12). Critically, we demonstrate control of the very early onset (VEO) IBD variant *Trim22* by *Ly75*, an *Ncf4*-interacting gene (13). Together we present a collective molecular mechanism for penetrating disease (fistulizing perianal type): broadly, *TRIM22* in VEO IBD, and in CGD, caused by genetic variation in *NCF4* p40 phox.

Citations

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